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Aminolysis of aspirin in acetonitrile

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Systems involving intramolecular participation of acidic and basic groups in ester aminolysis reactions in aprotic solvents have been studied for the relevance of catalysis to the mechanism of enzyme action,¹ and because of their applicability in racemisation-free methods of peptide synthesis.² Intramolecularly catalysed aminolyses of methyl¹ and phenyl³ salicylate, and 2-pyridyl *p*-nitrobenzoate⁴ followed the general rate equation for ester aminolyses in non-hydroxylic solvents:⁵

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ester}]}{dt} = (k_1[\text{Amine}] + k_2[\text{Amine}]^2) [\text{Ester}] \quad (\text{i})$$

In our experiments participation of the carboxy group (a common functional group of several enzymes) in the reaction of aspirin [I] with morpholine in acetonitrile has been studied. Rates were measured spectrophotometrically at 25°, under pseudo first order conditions. Surprisingly, the plot of the observed rate constants against morpholine concentration shows a pronounced saturation effect (see Fig, curve A), which

Fig

is typical in enzyme kinetics and characteristic of reactions involving complexation of reactants.⁶ The complex, C_m , indicated by the saturation kinetics for this reaction may be

an ion-pair, since in aprotic solvents ion-pair formation appears to be general for carboxylic acid – secondary amine interactions.⁷

The facts that addition of the stronger* base triethylamine to the reaction mixtures leads to considerable rate decreases (see Fig, curves B and C when triethylamine concentrations are $1.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$ and $2.86 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}$, respectively), and the reaction of methyl aspirin (II) takes place according to equation (i) ($k_1 = 4.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $k_2 = 1.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) also suggest a complex of acid-base nature.

Mechanisms 1 and 2 would account for the observed dependence of the aminolysis of compound (I) on the concentration of morpholine and triethylamine.

If mechanism 1/mechanism 2 is occurring, the reaction takes place through non-complexed/complexed species, while triethylamine and (I) form an unreactive complex C_t . Kinetically these two paths may not be differentiated. By a Michaelis-Menten type evaluation⁹ of our results, the constants for mechanisms 1 and 2 were found to be: $K_m = 4.4 \times 10^2 \text{M}^{-1}$, $K_t = 7.4 \times 10^3 \text{M}^{-1}$, $k = 8.1 \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, and $k' = 1.83 \times 10^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

*Triethylamine is a stronger base than morpholine in acetonitrile by 1.85 $\text{p}K_a$ units.⁸

The presence of the *o*-carboxyl group in compound (I) results not only in unusual kinetic behaviour, but also in enhanced reactivity. At [Morpholine] = 0.002 M (the lowest amine concentration studied) the k_{obs} for the reaction of (I) is more than 10^4 times greater than that for the reaction of (II). Experiments are in progress to clarify the mechanism of intramolecular assistance, which may be general acid-base, nucleophilic, or bifunctional catalysis.⁶

Received 13 January 1975

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